

At a semantic level, the combination of these terms is interesting, challenging, perhaps even contradictory. One implies order and rationality, the other spontaneity and irrationality. Fortunately, design has the capacity to bridge the semantic gap.

Design may be considered as a fundamental prerequisite for natural survival, as a loosely defined set of activities in which everyone indulges on a daily basis, or as a professional discipline which is tribal in the sense of gathering together diverse individuals in search of a common goal. The design tribes are also diverse, ranging in competence, knowledge and skills from the rigidly mathematical to the completely intuitive. Our specific interest is in the design of consumer products, and it is this design tribe who have the most diverse job of all.

The ultimate satisfaction of owning and using a product can only come from a coherent blend of the functional and the emotional: when manifest pleasure in the product aesthetic is reinforced by the knowledge that it is also easier to use, works better than the ugly one, and furthermore will endure longer. In product terms this is now identified as the search for - for want of better words - emotional satisfaction and joy in use. Here the ergonomics and design professions merge, and there is growing overlap and agreement on the aims and objectives, if not always on the methods and tools. Human factors researchers are beginning to deal with matters which previously have been the stock-in-trade of designers, and to attempt to apply scientific method to the search for understanding. The forms and interfaces of domestic product designs have often been the outcome of a magical process. The designer operates as a 'black box' - a magicians hat into which all parameters are poured and out of which pops the product rabbit. One section of the design profession has nurtured this mystery, while others have tried to understand and explain it. There remains a strong element within the design profession which regards all analysis of design activity as merely attempts to produce 'recipes' for those who can't to emulate those who can! Our objective is not to provide recipes for non-designers to become designers, but to provide tools for the design profession to do what they do better. At best, user centred design research is a stimulating and generative tool for the creative designer or design engineer to use, not only for product evaluation, but for product creation. Design plus emotion.

The rational plus the intuitive.

No conflict !

